

Polarographic Study of In(III) Complexes with Glycine and α -Alanine

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The polarographic behaviour of indium with glycine and α -alanine have been studied using a dropping mercury electrode. Single well defined three-electron reversible waves were obtained for In^{+3} - α -alanine and In^{+3} -glycine systems. The reduction was found to be diffusion controlled. Glycine and α -alanine formed 1:1 and 1:2 metal:ligand complexes with In(III) at $\text{pH} = 5.0$. The stability constants of In(III) -glycine and In(III) - α -alanine have been determined using Lingane and Deford-Hume methods. The pH effect has also been studied.

COMPLEX formation of glycine and α -alanine with some transition metal ions has been studied¹⁻⁴ using potentiometric techniques. The Fe(II, III) complexes with α -alanine and glycine have been studied in this laboratory^{5,6} using Rotated Platinum Electrode.

A survey of literature reveals that the reduction of In^{+3} at dropping mercury electrode has been studied in various complexing and non-complexing media by various investigators⁷⁻¹⁵. However complexation studies of In^{+3} with glycine and α -alanine have not been made. The present study was undertaken to investigate the composition and stability of the chelates of the said metal-ligand systems using dropping mercury electrode.

Experimental

These complexes have been studied at $\text{pH} 5$ using potassium hydrogen phthalate buffer. The ionic strength of the experimental solutions was kept constant at 0.2 by the addition of appropriate amount of NaClO_4 .

All the reagents used were of analytically pure grade. The α -alanine and glycine were obtained from B.D.H. (England) and were used as such. Indium nitrate (Schuchardt Munchen, Germany) solution was prepared in 0.2M perchloric acid medium and was standardized complexometrically¹⁶ using PAN indicator. All solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

An automatic polarograph type OH-102 (Radelkis, Hungary) was used for recording polarograms. Current-voltage curves were also recorded with a manual polarograph. Potentials were measured against SCE. The capillary had the following characteristics: $m = 2.370 \text{ mg sec}^{-1}$; $t = 3.36 \text{ sec}$ in 0.1M KCl; $h = 40 \text{ cms}$. Pure nitrogen was passed through the solutions before recording the polarograms. The pH of the solutions was measured with

a Radiometer (type TTT1d) pH meter using a glass electrode. All measurements were made at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using an ultrathermostat bath (MTA Kutesz, Budapest, Hungary E-149).

Results and Discussion

In pure supporting electrolyte (0.2M NaClO_4) In^{+3} ion does not give a well defined wave but in presence of $2.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}$ potassium hydrogen phthalate it produces a well defined reversible wave.

In^{+3} gave a reversible three-electron reduction wave both in the simple aquo and complex forms. The average value of log plot slope was found to be 0.020 ± 0.001 volt. The reductions of simple In^{+3} ion and In^{+3} -complex systems were found to be diffusion controlled as the plots of i vs $\sqrt{t}$ yielded straight lines passing through the origin.

Effect of pH

The half-wave potentials of metal-ligand systems (in a definite ratio) were shifted to more negative values on increasing the pH , indicating pH dependence of both In^{+3} -glycine and In^{+3} - α -alanine systems. For example by taking $\text{In}^{+3} = 2 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$, ligand (glycine) = $2 \times 10^{-2} \text{M}$ in 0.2M NaClO_4 and on increasing the pH from 1.5 to 5.0 the half-wave potential was shifted by 0.08V from -0.50 V to -0.60 V . However, precipitation occurred at $\text{pH} 5.5$ in 100 fold excess of the ligand and at $\text{pH} 6.0$ in presence of 400 fold excess of the ligand. Therefore, $\text{pH} 5.0$ was selected for all subsequent studies.

The following pK values for α -alanine and glycine have been reported¹⁷

	pK_1	pK_2
α -alanine	2.49	9.79
glycine	2.41	9.71

These values have been used to calculate the concentration of the respective acid anions ($[\text{X}^-]$).

Effect of Ligand Concentration

At pH 5.0 the half-wave potential of the metal ion ($\text{In(III)} - 2 \times 10^{-4} M$) was shifted to more negative values on increasing the concentration of the ligands (0.02 to 0.32 M i.e., 100 fold to 1600 fold) in 0.2 M NaClO_4 . The plot of $-E_{1/2}$ against $\log [\bar{X}]$ gave segmented curves as shown in Fig. 1. The values

of p (coordination number) determined from the equation

$$\Delta E_{1/2} / \Delta \log [\bar{X}] = -0.02p$$

Figure 1. Plots of $\log [X^-]$ against $-E_{1/2}$
 In(III)-Glycine ○ (A)
 In(III)- α -Alanine ● (B)

FIG. 3

Figure 2. Plots of $F_0(X)$ ○ (A)
 $F_1(X)$ ● (B)
 $F_2(X)$ ■ (C)
 against $[X^-]$ conc. of glycinate.

Figure 3. Plots of $F_0(X)$ ○ (A)
 $F_1(X)$ ● (B)
 $F_2(X)$ ■ (C)
 against $[X^-]$ conc. of α -alaninate.

were obtained as 1 and 2 in both these systems. Thus the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 metal-ligand chelates is indicated. The values of stability constants $\log \beta_1$ and $\log \beta_2$ for In(III)-glycine and In(III)- α -alanine system have been calculated by employing the methods of Lingane¹⁸ and Deford-Hume¹⁹ (Fig. 1, 2, 3). These are given in the table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS

	In(III)-Glycine		In(III)- α -Alanine	
	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$
Deford-Hume ¹⁹	10.25	16.21	9.85	15.93
Lingane Method ¹⁸	10.67	16.22	10.10	15.92

From the table 1, it is clear that the values of stability constant of the glycinate and α -alaninate complexes of In^{+3} are nearly the same. A comparison of the values of $\log \beta_1$ and $\log \beta_2$ shows that In^{+3} form slightly stronger complexes with glycine than with α -alanine which may be due to the presence of methyl group in the α -alanine molecule. The same trend of stability constants of glycine and α -alanine with some transition metal ions has been observed by other workers^{1,2,4} also.

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References

1. C. B. MONK, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1951, **47**, 285, 292, 297.
2. H. MATSUKAWA, M. OHTA, S. TAKATA and R. TSUCHIYA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1965, **38**, 1235.
3. F. BASOLO and YUNTI CHEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 953.
4. W. L. FELTY, C. G. EKSTROM and D. L. LEUSSING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 3006.
5. R. C. KAPOOR and K. C. K. MATHUR, *J. Polarogr. Soc.*, 1967, **13**, 86.
6. R. C. KAPOOR and J. K. JAILWAL, *Microchem. J.*, 1971, **16**, 501.
7. J. HEYROVSKY, *Chem. Listy.*, 1925, **18**, 198.
8. S. TAKAGI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 301.
9. J. TOMES, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1937, **9**, 12.
10. J. J. LINGANE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2099.
11. D. S. JAIN and K. ZUTSHI, *J. Less Commn. Metals*, 1965, **8**, 120.
12. PUSHPARAJA and M. SUDERSANAN, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. Sec. A*, 1974, **80**, 278.
13. R. S. RAMAKRISHNA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 2805.
14. J. N. GAUR, D. S. JAIN and M. M. PALRECHA, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 2201.
15. R. C. SRIVASTAVA and T. D. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 2192.
16. L. MEITES, 'Handbook of Analytical Chemistry', McGraw-Hill, New York, 1963, Ch. 3, p. 179.
17. D. D. PERRIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3125.
18. J. J. LINGANE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, **29**, 1.
19. D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5321.